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Why the World Does Not Exist

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Gabriel, Markus. *Why the World Does Not Exist*. (translated by Gregory S. Moss) Malden, MA: Polity Press, 2015; pp. vi + 239; ISBN: 978-0745687575 \$28.00 (hardcover)

Markus Gabriel is best known for his popular writings in Philosophy especially in the field of New Realism. The title of the book evokes curiosity and interest. Although, this book has been published in the year 2013, originally in the German language (Gabriel, Markus. *Warum Es Die Welt Nicht Gibt*. 2013), it has not been discussed much in Indian philosophical circles. So, I thought of reviewing the book with the intention of wowing readers to enjoy this particular book. New Realism is basically a rejection of the thesis that there is no direct perception of the world. It opposes the view that we do not perceive the world directly but have only a representation of it. Contrary to this notion, New Realism argues that our thoughts about facts that exist about the world and the world itself have equal weight. Here lies the importance of Gabriel's book. Gabriel argues that the world does not

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exist, because to designate the world as an all-encompassing reality or as the domain of all domains, the world must stand outside beyond all the references of ordinary occurrences. We can never have such a comprehensive, objective perspective from the outside. Hence the world does not exist. Frames of references, or in his words, ‘domains’ or ‘fields of sense’ occur only with respect to other frames of references. The end result is an infinite regress. He says, “The principle that the world does not exist entails that everything else exists” (1).

Gabriel desires to free philosophy from the clutches of conceptual jargons. It is often popularly thought and believed when something expressed or articulated in simple terms, it does not have philosophical weight. Contrary to this thinking, Gabriel tries to express his views and new nuances in simple language, so that they could be understood by people who do not have much background in philosophy. Noteworthy in this context is the appendix in the book, in which the philosophical concepts which he had capitalized throughout the book is explained. However, I must say that the book is not so easy to understand for the common people.

He begins the book with a need for thinking philosophy anew. In order to find out how reality is, one must discard everything that is created or added in the process of knowing. The central tendencies of Metaphysics and Postmodernism have brought in more ‘green glasses’¹ rather than avoiding them (Gabriel borrows the same expression from Kant and says constructivist are prey to it). The basic thrust of his thesis developed from the main principle of New Realism to which he is very much devoted. “New realism assumes that thoughts about facts exist with the same right as the facts at which our thoughts are directed” (6).

¹ Immanuel Kant uses the metaphor ‘green glasses’. The general idea of the green glasses metaphor is that, we have all green glasses on. And they are part of our brains how do we view the world and lead us to believe that everything is green.

In the first three chapters, Gabriel tries to convince the reader logically about the title of the book. He builds up his thesis with a fundamental question: What does it mean for something to exist at all? The whole book rotates around this perennial question. Gabriel defines, “Existence= appearing in a field of sense” (see Chapter II, “What is existence?” 50ff). By field of sense, he means, a frame of reference, or domain in which a determinate object appears in a certain way. Stemming from the assumption that field of sense is a sense in which an object appears, it can be vague and colourful. Presumably, the field of sense could be understood as background conditions or a stage for occurrences. (Gabriel does not use the words ‘background conditions’ and ‘stage for occurrences’) (67-72). Thus, the final conclusion establishes that “We cannot grasp the world conceptually because there is no field of sense to which it belongs” (76).

Automatically, the world does not exist, then the question arises, does a God exist? What is the meaning of religion and life? He discusses such questions in the second part of the book through the themes like Religion, the Infinite, Science, Consciousness, Art, among others (See chapters iv, v, vi). He criticizes that the scientific world view has failed ontologically and epistemologically. It is worth noting, according to him, the mistake of science and religion consists in the setting of one ‘field of sense’ as the ultimate field of sense or looking for one single frame of reference as the ultimate all-encompassing one, although there are infinite fields of sense. He calls this trend fetishism. An exception to this, or an antidote is art (see Chapter VI, “The Meaning of Art,” 184 ff). He says: “All objects appear in specific ways; they are presented to us in different ways. Everything always appears in a certain kind of light. Because objects can be presented in many different ways they can belong to many different fields of sense” (192).

Readers may tend to feel baffled by the idea that the world does not exist, or there is no God in the sense of a ‘Supreme Object’, then, how could we account for a meaningful existence? Many aspects of infinite domains instead offer comfort, “Everything we know is an aspect of Infinite” (219). Furthermore, “We live together in infinitely many

fields of sense which we are always rendering intelligible in new ways. What more could we want?" (208).

Since the first part of the book deals with the central idea of the book and receives markedly different answers for the quest, the second part of the book may seem not as interesting as the first; however, Gabriel succeeds in pursuing the fundamental question of the book till the end.

What I appreciate most in Gabriel, is his simple way of writing, making philosophy not to be confined to the elite alone. He quotes extensively and his thought experiments and examples from daily life and from television series make him accomplish his aim, "that every expert is an expert to the extent to which he can also communicate to the layman" (His interpretation on Ludwig Wittgenstein's famous maxim, "whatever can be said can be said clearly" 159-160).

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It is most unlikely everyone will agree with everything. Gabriel says, however, he could bring a welcome freshness to New Realism, monumentally shifting the way we understand the world. I must say that this book offers a lot to unmask the assumptions of our time, leaving readers constantly questioning what is real as they consider: "World?"

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